

Supplementary Material from “The metapopulation bridge to macroevolutionary speciation rates: a conceptual framework and empirical test”

Matheus Januario, Malin L. Pinsky, and Daniel L. Rabosky

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1 Part I: Markov Model

1.1 Overview:

In the Markovian chain described here, we will model $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ - i.e., a cell changing its state $\alpha \in 0, 1$ to another state in a posterior moment in time ($\beta \in 0, 1$). From that, we will derive a likelihood function to fit data on, which can be used to estimate parameters through maximum likelihood.

Model assumptions are shown in 1.2, notation in 1.3, and minor details related to the algebraic construction of the model in 1.4. Section 1.5 describes in detail how state change happens in the Markov model (i.e. it shows how $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$).

Section 1.6 shows the mathematical derivation of the model in detail, and section 1.7 illustrates how the probability transition works. Readers experienced with Markov Models are recommended to skip equations that are not numbered, as the amount of detail in the description can be slightly frustrating for experienced readers.

Section 1.8 shows how τ behaves as a measurement of the mean time to return to the equilibrium occupancy, how ϵ_{raw} behaves as the probability that a species occupy a patch (i.e. a metric of “commonness”). Section 1.9 discusses previous, analogous implementations of the model that can be found in the ecological literature.

Section 1.10 shows how to simulate data from our model, and section 1.11 discusses optimization through maximum likelihood, and shows an illustrative depiction of the likelihood surface associated with parameters.

1.2 Model assumptions:

- (1) The cell can only be occupied or unoccupied at a single moment in time. This means both α and β can only be equal to zero or one.
- (2) The cell changes its state as a function of colonization and extirpation rates. Meaning $P(\alpha \rightarrow \beta | c, e, \Delta t)$ and $P(\beta \rightarrow \alpha | c, e, \Delta t)$.
- (3) The modeled cell behaves independently from everything else (or, more accurately, the model ignores any other dependency but the metapopulation rates during cell state change).
- (4) Rates of colonization and extirpation can vary among species (i.e., datasets), but are constant through the time in which the cell was observed.
- (5) No two events (i.e., state transitions) can occur in the same infinitesimally small time step.

1.3 Notation:

$\Omega = 0, 1$ Is the set containing all possible states of a cell (i.e., it is the state space of the model)

$n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ represents the n th observation of the cell

$t_n \in \mathbb{N}$ represents the n th year in which the cell was observed

$\alpha \in \Omega$ represents the state of a cell in an anterior (usually $n-1$) moment in time.

$\beta \in \Omega$ represents the state of a cell in a posterior (usually n th) moment in time.

$\Delta t \in \mathbb{N}$ is defined as $t_n - t_{n-1}$

$c \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is the rate at which colonizations occur.

$e \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is the rate at which extirpations occur.

$P_n(T_{\alpha\beta}|c, e, \Delta t) \in [0, 1]$ is the probability, *due only to the Markov Model*, of the cell being in state β at the n th time, given the cell was in state α , at a moment Δt distant in the past.

$X = \psi_1, \dots, \psi_N$ is a vector containing the data discussed in this text in section 1.11 and beyond, which corresponds to a vector with all probabilities of occurrence, ordered from past to future.

1.4 Technical points

Ω is a direct consequence of the first assumption. Thus, $P_n(\alpha = 1) + P_n(\alpha = 0) = 1$ and $P_n(\beta = 1) + P_n(\beta = 0) = 1$

Consequently, all 4 possible events that can happen in an infinitesimally small time interval $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ are:

- (I) An colonization occurred in the cell - i.e., $T_{01|\Delta t} : [\alpha_{t-\Delta t} = 0] \rightarrow [\beta_t = 1]$
- (II) Cell kept unoccupied - i.e., $T_{00|\Delta t} : [\alpha_{t-\Delta t} = 0] \rightarrow [\beta_t = 0]$
- (III) An extirpation occurred in the cell - i.e., $T_{10|\Delta t} : [\alpha_{t-\Delta t} = 1] \rightarrow [\beta_t = 0]$
- (IV) Cell kept occupied - i.e., $T_{11|\Delta t} : [\alpha_{t-\Delta t} = 1] \rightarrow [\beta_t = 1]$

However, as the time interval Δt grows, more than one event can happen within that time window.

We can attribute probabilities of such events, labeling them as $P(T_{01}|c, e, \Delta t)$, $P(T_{00}|c, e, \Delta t)$, $P(T_{10}|c, e, \Delta t)$, $P(T_{11}|c, e, \Delta t)$, respectively.

As those are all events that can happen, then: $P(T_{01}|c, e, \Delta t) + P(T_{00}|c, e, \Delta t) + P(T_{10}|c, e, \Delta t) + P(T_{11}|c, e, \Delta t) = 1$.

1.5 Markov chain evolution

The Markov chain we are interested in here is defined as a process where a function F connects two states by a probability measure. I.e., where $F : \mathcal{X} \times [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$.

Specifically, to evolve our Markov model, we use the following algorithm:

1. Set the first state of our cell (i.e., alpha), and set the first time step $n = 1$
2. Sample U from a uniform distribution in the interval $[0, 1]$.
3. Set a $\Delta t = t_n + y$, with $y \in R^+$
4. If $\alpha = 1$:
 - 4.A) If $U \leq P(T_{10}|c, e, \Delta t)$, then $\beta = 0$; otherwise, $\beta = 1$

If $\alpha = 0$:

- 4.B) If $U \leq P(T_{01}|c, e, \Delta t)$, then $\beta = 1$; otherwise, $\beta = 0$
5. Update n to the next time step $n = n + 1$,
6. Store β in a vector, and then update $\alpha_n = \beta_{n-1}$
7. Go to step 2, and cycle (steps 2-7) until $n = N$.

At the end of the process, this will result in a vector of length N made only with zeros and ones.

1.6 Deriving transition probabilities

This section is focused on deriving the probability that our focal cell is occupied *only due to the Markov Model* and a time interval Δt . Formally, we want to calculate $P(\beta = 1|\alpha = 0, \Delta t, c, e)$

From the technical points (section 1.4) we can write the equation:

$$P(\beta = 1|\alpha = 0, \Delta t, c, e) = (1 - e\Delta t) \times P(\alpha = 0|t_n) + (c\Delta t) \times (1 - P(\alpha = 0|t_n)) \quad (1)$$

Which represents the only two things that can change a cell's state: extirpation (left term) and colonization (right term).

Note that in equation (1), there is no account for imperfect observation. This means that this model describes a system that can be **perfectly observed**. In other words, there are no false positive or false negative observations (but note we will break this assumption in section 2).

Models that use strings of presences and absences **and** want to account for imperfect detection may want to refer to [Mackenzie et al 2003, Ecology 84\(8\)](#), [Kery \(2010, chapter 20\)](#), or [Dorazio & Royle \(2005, J. Amer. Stat. Assoc. 100\(470\)\)](#).

Now, we can simplify notation by writing $P(\alpha = 1|c, e, t) = P_{(1|t)}$ and $P(\beta = 1|\alpha = 0, \Delta t, c, e) = P_{(01|\Delta t)}$

Then using equation (1):

$$P_{(01|\Delta t)} = P_{(1|t)} - e\Delta t \times P_{(1|t)} + c\Delta t - c\Delta t P_{(1|t)}$$

And rearranging it:

$$P_{(01|\Delta t)} - P_{(1|t)} = -e\Delta t \times P_{(1|t)} + c\Delta t - c\Delta t P_{(1|t)} \quad (2)$$

Now, dividing both sides of equation (2) by Δt :

$$\frac{P_{(01|\Delta t)} - P_{(1|t)}}{\Delta t} = c - (c + e)P_{(1|t)}$$

If we take $\lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0}$ in this new equation, we will have:

$$\frac{dP_{(01|t)}}{dt} = c - (c + e) \times P_{(1|t)} \quad (3)$$

This is a first-order ordinary differential equation, which when solved leads to:

$$P(\beta = 1|\alpha = 0, \Delta t, c, e) = A \times \exp(-(c + e)\Delta t) + \frac{c}{(c + e)} \quad (4)$$

When A is a constant that will depend on the initial condition (i.e. if $\alpha = 1$ or if $\alpha = 0$).

We can know this constant by setting $\Delta t = 0$ and getting that:

$$P_{(\beta=1|t=0)} = A \times 1 + \frac{c}{(c+e)}$$

By assigning $P_{(01|t=0)} = w_0$, we can see that:

$$A = w_0 - \frac{c}{(c+e)}$$

Plugging the above in equation (4), we get:

$$P(\beta = 1|\alpha = 0, \Delta t, c, e) = (w_0 - \frac{c}{(c+e)}) \times \exp(-(c + e)\Delta t) + \frac{c}{(c+e)}$$

Which is equal to:

$$P(\beta = 1|\alpha = 0, \Delta t, c, e) = w_0 \times \exp(-(c + e)\Delta t) + \frac{c - [c \times \exp(-(c + e)\Delta t)]}{(c + e)} \quad (5)$$

By an analogous procedure, we get that:

$$P(\beta = 0|\alpha = 1, \Delta t, c, e) = w_0 \times \exp(-(c + e)\Delta t) + \frac{e - [e \times \exp(-(c + e)\Delta t)]}{(c + e)} \quad (6)$$

We can finally write our R function that calculates the next state given an inputted state:

```
# For convenience, in the function I will use t instead of Delta t
P01=function(w0=0, c,e,t){ # w0 = 0 is the solution chosen by in Alonso et al (2015) ecol. lett.
  mu= exp(-(c+e)*t)
  aux = w0 * mu + ((c-c*mu)/(c+e))
  return(aux)
}

P10=function(w0=0, c,e,t){ # w0 = 0 is the solution chosen by Alonso et al (2015) ecol. lett.
  mu= exp(-(c+e)*t)
  aux = w0 * mu + ((e-e*mu)/(c+e))
  return(aux)
}
```

From equation (5) we can get that:

$$P(\beta = 0|\alpha = 0, c, e, \Delta t) = 1 - P(\beta = 1|\alpha = 0, c, e, \Delta t) \text{ and:}$$

From equation (6) we can get that

$$P(\beta = 1|\alpha = 1, c, e, \Delta t) = 1 - P(\beta = 0|\alpha = 1, c, e, \Delta t)$$

Which together represent equation set (1), in the main text.

1.7 Visualizing the model

We can visualize how $P(\beta = 1|\alpha = 0, \Delta t, c, e)$ (i.e., Equation 5) change according with Δt , c , and e :

```
cs=c(0.05, 0.1, 0.5)
es=c(0.05, 0.1, 0.5)
to_plot=data.frame()
for(j in 1:length(cs)){
  for(k in 1:length(es)){
    P0s = seq(0,1, length.out = 30)
    tt=seq(0,5, by=0.1)

    res=data.frame()
    for(i in 1:length(P0s)){
      aux = P01(w0 = P0s[i], c = cs[j], e = es[k], tt)
      res=rbind(res, aux)
    }
    colnames(res)=tt
    colnames(res)[1]="P0"

    to_plot_aux=reshape2::melt(res, id.vars="P0")
    colnames(to_plot_aux)=c("P0", "time", "Prob")
    to_plot_aux$time=as.numeric(to_plot_aux$time)
    to_plot_aux$c=paste0("c = ", cs[j])
    to_plot_aux$e=paste0("e = ", es[k])

    to_plot=rbind(to_plot, to_plot_aux)
  }
}
```

We can plot the change in probability as a continuum:

```
ggplot(to_plot, aes(x=time, y=P0, fill=Prob))+
  facet_wrap(c~e)+
  geom_tile()+
  scale_fill_viridis_c(option = "magma")+
  ylab("P(1|t=0)")+
  xlab("Time")+
  labs(fill="P(1|t)")+
  theme_minimal()+
  theme(legend.position = "bottom")
```

So, we see that the higher the turnover rate ($\tau = c + e$), the faster the system gets to its equilibrium value, which is $P^* = P(\beta = 1|t \rightarrow \inf, c, e) = c/(c + e)$ (to know why see next section “Summarizing the predictions

Figure 1: Continuous prediction of occupancy probability of single cell. See figure 2 for a version of this figure binned by quartiles.

of the model”). We can also emphasize some key quantiles of $P(\beta = 1|\alpha = 0, \Delta t, c, e)$ to make the plot easier to visualize (figure 2):

```
ggplot(to_plot, aes(x=time, y=P0, fill=Prob))+
  facet_wrap(c~e)+
  geom_tile()+
  scale_fill_viridis_b(option = "magma")+
  ylab("Initial probability of presence P(1|t=0)")+
  xlab("Time")+
  labs(fill="P(1|t)")+
  theme_minimal()+
  theme(legend.position = "bottom")
```

1.8 Summarizing the predictions of the model

We can also analytically calculate the equilibrium state of this model using equation (3):

$$\frac{d}{dt}P_{(1|t)} = c - (c + e) \times P_{(1|t)}$$

$$0 = c - (c + e)P_{(1|t \rightarrow Inf)}$$

$$(c + e)P_{(1|t \rightarrow Inf)} = c$$

$$P_{(1|t \rightarrow Inf)} = \frac{c}{(c+e)} = P^*$$

Which is exactly what we observed in the plots of the section “Visualizing the model” when the rates are fast enough. In other words, what the model says is that, in the long run, the probability that a cell is occupied tends to equal the proportion of the metapopulation turnover that can be attributed to colonizations (i.e., $\epsilon_{raw} = \frac{c}{(c+e)}$). Due to the sampling employed (see details in the main text), species with the same ϵ_{raw} will be interpreted as being equally “common”, even though the extent of occupancy (number of cells) can be different (but see analytical issues related to truncation of ϵ_{raw} , described in supplementary section 3.2). In the sampling scheme adopted in the main text, the number of patches is arbitrary (and emerges from a specific sampling within a specific grid spatial scale), and we want to separate the effect of range size (extent of occurrence) from the effect of metapopulation turnover. Thus, ϵ_{raw} measures commonness in a way that is independent of range size (and, in our opinion, still captures commonness: it will approximate the probability of observing a patch as occupied at any time).

Importantly, a consequence of the modeling shown above is that metapopulation-level persistence is a function of both biological attributes and environmental suitability. Patch suitability in turn affects c and e and thus is also deeply connected to the way a species persist.

Another important aspect is that there is no “metapopulation size” in our model, in the same way that “Hanski-like” metapopulations have an associated size for each habitat patch. The closest quantity to “size” in our metapopulations is the number of patches where they could occur (that is why they are closer to “Levins-like” metapopulations), and this “size” is totally dependent on the sampling that was done. For the empirical case described in the main text, however, this becomes a caveat: The lack of clearly discrete habitats that can be assigned as specific patches is one of the limitations of assuming metapopulations exist in the ocean (Grimm et al, 2003).

Appart form commonness, one can also see that the turnover rate (i.e., $\tau_{raw} = (c + e)$) tells *how fast* this equilibrium probability (e_{raw}) is reached. We can actually calculate this time until the equilibrium probability is approached. Formally speaking, the equilibrium probability will never be reached if the Markov process

Figure 2: Continuous prediction of occupancy probability of a single cell. In this plot, colors are binned in 4 classes for easier visualization. See figure 1 for a continuous version of this figure.

starts away from said equilibrium, but we can calculate the time t where the difference between $P_{(1|\Delta t)}$ and P^* is smaller than a threshold ϕ . So:

$$P_{(1|\Delta t)} - P^* < \phi$$

$$P_{(1|\Delta t)} - \frac{c}{(c+e)} < \phi$$

$$(w_0 - \frac{c}{(c+e)}) \times \exp(-(c+e)\Delta t) + \frac{c}{(c+e)} - \frac{c}{(c+e)} < \phi$$

$$(w_0 - \frac{c}{(c+e)}) \times \exp(-(c+e)\Delta t) < \phi$$

We can consider just the distance:

$$|w_0 - \frac{c}{(c+e)}| \times \exp(-(c+e)\Delta t) < \phi$$

If we solve for ϕ , we get the following equations:

$$t^* = -\frac{\log(-\frac{\phi(c+e)}{ew_0+c(w_0-1)})}{e+c}; \text{ when } W_0 < \frac{c}{c+e}, \text{ and:}$$

$$t^* = -\frac{\log(\frac{\phi(c+e)}{ew_0+c(w_0-1)})}{e+c}; \text{ when } W_0 > \frac{c}{c+e}$$

So if, for example, we set $\phi = 0.0001$ and $w_0 = 0.5$, we get the following expected “waiting times” until a region close to equilibrium is reached:

```
phi = 0.0001
rates = seq(0.01, 1, length.out = 15)
Inits0cc = seq(0.1, 1, by=0.1)
to_plot=data.frame()
for(0cc0 in Inits0cc){
  to_plot_aux=data.frame(
    c=rep(rates, times=length(rates)),
    e=rep(rates, each=length(rates)),
    0cc0 = 0cc0,
    t2star=NA)

  for(i in 1:nrow(to_plot_aux)){
    c_i = to_plot_aux$c[i]
    e_i = to_plot_aux$e[i]
    eq_i = c_i/(c_i+e_i)

    if(0cc0 > eq_i){
      to_plot_aux$t2star[i] = -(log(+1*(phi *(c_i+e_i))/(e_i*0cc0+c_i*(0cc0-1)))/(e_i+c_i))
    }else if(0cc0 < eq_i){
      to_plot_aux$t2star[i] = -(log(-1*(phi *(c_i+e_i))/(e_i*0cc0+c_i*(0cc0-1)))/(e_i+c_i))
    }else if(0cc0 == eq_i){
      to_plot_aux$t2star[i] = 0
    }

    to_plot = rbind(to_plot, to_plot_aux)
  }
}
```

```

to_plot$Occ0 = paste0("initial occ. = ", to_plot$Occ0)

ggplot(to_plot, aes(x=c, y=e, fill=log(t2star, base=2)))+
  facet_wrap(~Occ0, nrow=2)+
  geom_tile()+
  scale_fill_viridis_c(na.value = "white")+
  theme_minimal()+
  xlab("colonization rate")+
  ylab("extirpation rate")+
  labs(fill="Log2 Time until eq.")+
  theme(legend.position = "bottom")

```


Figure 3: Time until equilibrium under different combinations of colonization and extinction rates. Panels show different initial conditions (occupied patches). Note the turnover rate (summation of both rates) dominates this quantity.

As we can see, the “time until equilibrium is reached” (i.e., t^*), in this Markov model is dominated (when compared to the initial state α) by the turnover rate $\tau_{raw} = c + e$, and the equilibrium probability of a cell being occupied will be described by $\epsilon_{raw} = \frac{c}{c+e} = P^*$. Thus, ϵ_{raw} and τ_{raw} are quantities that describe the behaviors we are interested in studying persistence: τ_{raw} measures the amount of time until the Occupancy equilibrium value is reached, while $\epsilon_{raw} = P^*$ measures the proportions of cells at equilibrium. We use the *raw* subscript due to analytical reasons discussed in the main text (section “Measuring persistence”).

1.9 Independent derivations of the same model

This model was derived from first principles multiple times before. For instance, equation (1) above is the same as equation (2) in [Alonso et al \(2015, Ecol. Lett. 18\(5\)\)](#), which is in many ways a re-derivation of [MacArthur and Wilson’s Island Biogeography Theory](#). In particular, equation (2) is analogous to equation (11) in [Simberloff \(1969, Ecology 50\(2\)\)](#). Equation (4) here is also analogous to equation (3) in [Alonso et al \(2015, Ecol. Lett. 18\(5\)\)](#).

Consequently, if we set $w_0 = 0$, in equation (5), we get that:

$$P_{(1|\Delta t)} = \left(0 - \frac{c}{(c+e)}\right) \times \exp(-(c+e)\Delta t) + \frac{c}{(c+e)} = \frac{c}{(c+e)} \times [1 - \exp(-(c+e) * \Delta t)]$$

which is equal to equation (4) in Alonso et al (2015, Ecol. Lett. 18(5)).

Finally, for the reader more familiar with phylogenetic methods, this model is also equal to the “ARD” model of Paradis et al (2004 *Bioinformatics* 20(2)). In the special case where $c = e$, the model is also equal to Pagel’s (1994, *Proc. Roy. Soc. B.* 255(1342)) model, also known as the “MK model” in Lewis, (2001, *Sys. Bio.* 50(6)), or as “SYM” model in Paradis et al (2004, *Bioinformatics* 20(2)). Note however that although the core mathematics is the same, in phylogenetic models the likelihood function integrates over the possible states that the ancestor of a branch might have had, while in the implementation here (see below) we integrate over the uncertainty in the time series of presence-absence. This integration is not emphasized in the notation employed in any of the aforementioned references, and in our view this is important because many other types of data, if ordered temporally (i.e. quaternary probabilities of occurrence in a spatial grid) could produce ψ_t , and using this integration allows estimation of metapopulation parameters with through straightforward incorporation of uncertainties in occupancy.

1.10 Simulating data under the model with perfect detection

Now we can plug equation (5) in the algorithm described in the section “Markov chain evolution”, and write the following simulating function to simulate the Markov process described in section 1.5:

```
simMarkovMetapop=function(X, c, e, deltat){
  states= c(0,1)
  if(! (X %in% states | length(X)>1)){
    stop("X must be zero or one")
  }

  if(X==1){
    Pxchange = P10(c = c, e = e, t = deltat)
  }else{
    Pxchange = P01(c = c, e = e, t = deltat)
  }

  U = runif(1)

  if(U<=Pxchange){
    return(states[!states %in% X])
  }else{
    return(X)
  }
}
```

And we can simulate many datasets with this function:

```
genDataSetsMetapop=function(ndatasets=1, c, e, nob=10, times=NULL){
  data=data.frame()
  for(dts in 1:ndatasets){
    # get random times where the system was observed:
    if(is.null(times)){
      time = sort(sample(1970:2014, size=nob))
    }else{
      if(is.numeric(times)){

```

```

    time = sort(times)
  }else{
    stop("times was wrongly specified")
  }
}

#get a initial state:
X = sample(c(0,1), size = 1)

for(i in 2:length(time)){
  nextX = simMarkovMetapop(X = X[i-1], # state
                           c = c, # colonization rate
                           e = e, # extirpation rate
                           deltat = time[i]-time[i-1] #delta t
                          )
  X = c(X, nextX)
}
aux=data.frame(X = X, time=time, sim=dts)
data=rbind(data, aux)
}

colnames(data) = c("ppres_mu", "year", "cell")
return(data)
}

data = genDataSetsMetapop(ndatasets = 30, c = .1, e = .4, nobs = 12)
head(data)

```

```

##   ppres_mu year cell
## 1         0 1971    1
## 2         0 1973    1
## 3         1 1976    1
## 4         1 1977    1
## 5         0 1987    1
## 6         0 1988    1

```

Which we can then plot (figure 4):

```

ggplot(data, aes(x=year, y=cell, fill=as.factor(ppres_mu)))+
  geom_abline(slope = rep(0, times=max(data$cell)),
             intercept = 1:max(data$cell), col="grey75")+
  geom_point(pch=21)+
  scale_fill_manual(values = c("white", "black"))+
  xlab("Time")+
  ylab("Simulation")+
  theme_classic()+
  labs(fill="Cell state (when sampled)")+
  theme(legend.position = "bottom")

```


Figure 4: Illustration of simulated of data under perfect detection. Fill circles mean presence and empty circles mean absence

1.11 Optimizing parameters through maximum likelihood

Now, we can use the data we simulated to estimate the maximum likelihood of our (perfectly observed) data.

With equations (5) and (6) shown above, we can measure the probability of all 4 possible events that can happen in a time interval Δt (i.e. the ones in the section “Technical points”, which also correspond to the set of equations 1 in the main text). We can visualize these equations by doing the following:

```
deltat = seq(0, 10, by=0.01)
cc = .9
ee = .45
deltat=seq(0,10, by=.1)

plot(NA, xlim=range(deltat), ylim = c(0,1),
     ylab="Probability", xlab="Delta t",
     frame.plot = F,
     main = expression(paste("P(0", beta, ")")))

#P01
polygon(col="skyblue2",border = NA,
        x = c(deltat, rev(deltat)),
        y = c(P01(c = cc, e = ee, t = deltat), rep(0, times=length(deltat))))

#P11
polygon(col="skyblue4",border = NA,
        x = c(deltat, rev(deltat)),
        y = c(P01(c = cc, e = ee, t = deltat), rep(1, times=length(deltat))))

text(y=(cc/(cc+ee))*0.5, x=8, labels = "P01", col="white", cex=2)
text(y=((cc/(cc+ee))*1.15, x=8, labels = "P00", col="white", cex=2)
```

```
plot(NA, xlim=range(deltat), ylim = c(0,1),
     ylab="Probability", xlab="Delta t",
     frame.plot = F,
     main = expression(paste("P(1", beta, ")")))

#P01
polygon(col="firebrick1",border = NA,
        x = c(deltat, rev(deltat)),
        y = c(P10(c = cc, e = ee, t = deltat), rep(0, times=length(deltat))))

polygon(col="firebrick4",border = NA,
        x = c(deltat, rev(deltat)),
        y = c(P10(c = cc, e = ee, t = deltat), rep(1, times=length(deltat))))

text(y=(ee/(cc+ee))*0.5, x=8, labels = "P10", col="white", cex=2)
text(y=((ee/(cc+ee))*1.5, x=8, labels = "P11", col="white", cex=2)
```

So, the likelihood of a dataset being generated by a set of rates is equal to the probability of all its transitions:

$$Lik(c, e|X) = \prod_{n=2}^N P(\alpha_{n-1} \rightarrow \beta_n | c, e, \Delta t) \quad (7)$$

Figure 5: Illustration of first and second equations from main text equation set (1) (also equation (5) here), assuming $c = 0.9$ and $e = 0.45$

Figure 6: Illustration of third and fourth equations from main text equation set (1) (also equation (6) here), assuming $c = 0.9$ and $e = 0.45$

Note that the equation above (i.e., equation 2 in the main text) is analogous to equation A7 in the supplementary material of Alonso et al (2015).

We can implement equation (7) in the R function `loglik(cc,ee)`, below:

```
# Get the transition probabilities:
P01=function(c,e,t){
  mu= exp(-(c+e)*t)
  aux = 0 * mu + ((c-c*mu)/(c+e))
  return(aux)
}

P10=function(c,e,t){
  mu= exp(-(c+e)*t)
  aux = 0 * mu + ((e-e*mu)/(c+e))
  return(aux)
}

# Notice also that we will use the log likelihood space instead
# of the standard probability space to keep estimate precision.
loglik = function(cc,ee){

  LOGLIK=0
  for(j in unique(dt$cell)){
    aux = dt[dt$cell==j,]

    if(nrow(aux)>1){
      p=aux$ppres_mu
      time=aux$year

      for(i in 2:length(p)){
        deltat = time[i]-time[i-1]

        aux_lik =
          (1-P10(c = cc, e = ee, t=deltat)) * p[i-1] * p[i] + # 1 > 1 :
          P01(c = cc, e = ee, t=deltat) * (1-p[i-1]) * p[i] + # 0 > 1 :
          P10(c = cc, e = ee, t=deltat) * p[i-1] * (1-p[i]) + # 1 > 0
          (1-P01(c = cc, e = ee, t=deltat)) * (1-p[i-1]) * (1-p[i]) # 0 > 0
        LOGLIK = LOGLIK + log(aux_lik)
      }
    }
  }
  return(-LOGLIK) # just to use default minimization of optim
}

# notice data will be treated as fixed and should be
# already loaded in r workspace for the function to work.
csim=runif(1)
csim
```

```
## [1] 0.6280257
```

```
esim=runif(1)
esim
```

```
## [1] 0.02845769
```

```
dt = genDataSetsMetapop(ndatasets = 50, c = csim, e = esim, nobs = 40)
```

```
# testing the function:
loglik(.1, .1)
```

```
## [1] 425.5515
```

We can then plot the likelihood surface for a given dataset using the following function (figure 7):

```
plotLogLikSurface=function(nlevels=50){

  c=seq(0.001,3,length.out = 20)
  e=seq(0.001,3,length.out = 20)

  likMac = Vectorize(FUN = loglik, vectorize.args = c("cc","ee"))
  title = "Log Lik surface"

  surf.mat = outer(c, e, likMac) # loglik surface
  contour(c, e, surf.mat, xlab="Colonization rate",
          ylab="Extirpation rate", nlevels=nlevels,
          col = MJtools::makeColorScale2(1:nlevels,
          hcl.palette = "Reds", ncol = nlevels, rev = FALSE),
          main=title) # contour graph

}

#testing function:
plotLogLikSurface()

# we can easily optimize it:
toOptim=function(params){
  return(loglik(params[1], params[2]))
}
init= c(.5, .5)
names(init) = c("cc", "ee")
res_rates = optim(par = init, fn = toOptim)

# visualizing estimated vs simulated:
points(x = csim, y=esim, col=MJtools::makeTransparent("black", alpha = 175), pch=16, cex=2)
points(x = res_rates$par[1], y=res_rates$par[2], col="blue", pch=4, cex=3, lwd=2)
```

Now, there is an important detail: [Batt et al \(2017, Ecol. Lett. 20\(9\)\)](#) have data that represent uncertainties in terms of the state of each cell in a given point t_n in time. In other words, observations in the data used here, labeled as $\psi_n \in [0, 1]$ represent *probabilities of states*, instead of the actual states.

Because our likelihood function only “sees” state transitions (i.e., equation (8)), we can assign probabilities of each of the four transitions happening, by assigning:

Figure 7: Illustration of Log-likelihood surface for a given dataset under different values of colonization and extirpation rates. Black dot shows simulated values and the blue cross show the estimated values of rates.

$$P(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) = P_{n-1}(\alpha) \times P_n(\beta)$$

Where $P_{n-1}(\alpha) = \psi_{n-1}$ if $\alpha = 1$ and
 $P_{n-1}(\alpha) = (1 - \psi_{n-1})$ if $\alpha = 0$.

the same happens for β , so
 $P_{n-1}(\beta) = \psi_{n-1}$ if $\beta = 1$ and
 $P_{n-1}(\beta) = (1 - \psi_{n-1})$ if $\beta = 0$.

Putting the above together in equation (8), we have that:

$$\begin{aligned} Lik(c, e|X) = \prod_{n=2}^N \psi_{n-1} \times \psi_n \times P(11|c, e, \Delta t) + \\ \psi_{n-1} \times (1 - \psi_n) \times P(10|c, e, \Delta t) + \\ (1 - \psi_{n-1}) \times (1 - \psi_n) \times P(00|c, e, \Delta t) + \\ (1 - \psi_{n-1}) \times 1 - \psi_n \times P(01|c, e, \Delta t) \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

Which is main text's equation (2) (and the actual function implemented in R's object `loglik(cc, ee)`).

2 Part II: Evaluating Markov model power through simulation of noisy data

2.1 Overview

In this section, we will focus on the noisiness of the data analysed in the main text. In particular, in section 2.2 we break the assumption of perfect observation which we adopted in section 1. For this, we will also assume a specific model for the “degeneration” of information that can, possibly, happen with real datasets. In section 2.3 we introduce h , a statistic that measures the information content of a dataset (and can be applied in both simulated and empirical situations). Then, in section 2.4 we conduct a formal power analysis, to measure the ability of our model to correctly infer the simulated parameters under a range of information degeneration. We describe the results of this power analysis in section 2.5, and discuss them in section 2.6. Finally, in section 2.7 we briefly explore the information content of the empirical dataset employed in the main text.

2.2 Breaking the assumption of perfect observation

To investigate the robustness of this model, we will introduce imperfect observation. In particular, we will degenerate data following a model that introduces uncertainty in the states, to simulate data that resembles the estimates produced by Batt et al (2019). We want to have some “control” over how much information is degenerated, so we will build a particular mathematical model that degenerates information in a perfectly observed dataset.

First, we will assume *false positives* (i.e. *observed presence when true absence*) *never happen*, and deal only with the effect of **false negatives** (i.e., observed absence when true presence).

As mentioned in the section “Deriving transition probabilities”, to account for imperfect observation in raw data (not ψ_n), one can use strings of presences and absences collected under *Pollock's robust design* (see [Pollock, \(1982 Jour. Wildlife Manag. 46\(3\)\)](#) to simultaneously estimate the probability of presence and the

Markov parameters. When this is not possible (or desirable) what one can do is to independently estimate ψ_n and then fit the Markov model, integrating over the uncertainty of states in the dataset (as we did in section 1.11).

Below, we will simulate $X = \psi_1, \dots, \psi_N$, which is a sequence X made of many probabilities $\psi_n \in [0, 1]$ that represent the probability that our focal cell is occupied in that sampling moment - in other words, $\psi_n = P(\text{state}_n = 1)$.

Our ability to accurately estimate parameters, of course, will depend both on (A) the detectability being high enough for the collected data to have information on the occupation of that cell at the n th observation, and (B) of the capacity of the whole dataset to have preserved enough structure (i.e., have enough *transitions*) to allow parameter estimation.

To keep our simulations simple, let's use the parameter ρ to represent the capacity of the model to preserve information. To aid interpretations, we want this parameter to be in a space $\rho \in [0, 1]$, so ρ can represent completely the spectrum between no information at all $\rho = 0$ and as much information as a dataset X can carry (i.e., $\rho = 1$).

We will take the (arguably arbitrary) decision to model the noise presence estimation by using a beta distribution parameterized with $\mu = \rho$ and sample size $\nu \in R^+$.

To check if this beta abstraction makes sense, in the context of Batt et al's (2017) estimates, let's first look at the case where $\nu \rightarrow 0$. We choose this arbitrary value of ν because it matches almost exactly the variance estimates for each psi_n in Batt's dataset, as shown in the figure 8 (below) where the x-axis represents ψ_n estimated by Batt et al, 2017 (ecol. Lett. - and equivalent to the ρ_n we will simulate soon) and the y axis show the variance of the estimate. The red line below shows the variance (y-axis) of a Beta distribution with a certain $\mu = \rho$ (x-axis) and $\nu_{\lim \rightarrow 0}$. To run the code though, we operationalize this in the code by setting $\nu = 10^{-15}$.

These beta distributions would have the following density (figure 9):

```
#colors of probabilities:
#warmer colors mean higher mean probabilities:
Pobs = seq(0.1, 1, by=0.1)
cols = MetBrewer::met.brewer("Hiroshige", n = length(Pobs), direction = -1)

plot(NA, xlim=c(0,1), ylim=c(0,2E-12),
     xlab="phi_n", ylab="Density")
qBeta = seq(0, 1, by=0.001)
for(i in 1:length(Pobs)){
  muBeta = Pobs[i]
  nuBeta = 10E-15
  alfa = muBeta *nuBeta
  beta = (1-muBeta)*nuBeta

  lines(x = qBeta,
        y = dbeta(x = qBeta, shape1 = alfa, shape2 = beta),
        col=cols[i], lwd=3)
}
points(x = Pobs, y= rep(-2.5E-14, times=length(Pobs)), col=cols, pch=16)
```

So, even though the fit above is clearly very good (Supp. fig. 8), we will not follow exactly this beta distribution because this density does not change much of the original data. So we will stick with the beta model, but use $\nu = 10$ to generate noise in our observations. This beta distribution results in the following betas (figure 10) - that to me seem to capture better a notion on “controlled” noise (we want to use this control later in the interpretation of our analysis).

Figure 8: Comparison of beta model and Batt et al (2017) data. The red line illustrates the mean and the variance of a beta distribution with different averages (x-axis) and sample size equal to 10^{-15} . Black points show mean and variances of ρ estimates in the empirical (Batt et al, 2017) dataset.

Figure 9: Illustration of the density of many beta distributions with different averages (colors) and sample size $\nu = 10^{-15}$

```

#colors of probabilities:
#warmer colors mean higher probabilities:
cols = MetBrewer::met.brewer("Hiroshige", n = length(Pobs), direction = -1)

plot(NA, xlim=c(0,1), ylim=c(0,10),
     xlab="Mu", ylab="Density")
qBeta = seq(0, 1, by=0.001)
for(i in 1:length(Pobs)){
  muBeta = Pobs[i]
  nuBeta = 10
  alfa = muBeta *nuBeta
  beta = (1-muBeta)*nuBeta

  lines(x = qBeta,
        y = dbeta(x = qBeta, shape1 = alfa, shape2 = beta),
        col=cols[i], lwd=3)
}
points(x = Pobs, y= rep(-2.5E-14, times=length(Pobs)), col=cols, pch=16)

```


Figure 10: Illustration of the density of a beta distribution with different averages (colors) and sample size equal to 10.0

The function that simulates datasets with this “model” of noisy detection is the following:

```

genDataSetsMetapopRho=function(ndatasets=1, cc, ee, nobs, times=NULL, rho=1){
  data=data.frame()
  for(dts in 1:ndatasets){

    # get random times where the system was observed:
    if(is.null(times)){

      if(nobs>(2014-1970)){
        tgt_yr = 1970+nobs
      }else{
        tgt_yr = 2014
      }
      time = sort(sample(1970:tgt_yr, size=nobs))
    }else{
      if(is.numeric(times)){
        time = sort(times)
      }else{
        stop("times was wrongly specified")
      }
    }
  }

  #get a initial state sampling form the stationary probabilities:
  X = sample(c(0,1), prob = c(ee/(cc+ee), cc/(cc+ee)), size = 1)

  # simulate timestep by timestep
  for(i in 2:length(time)){
    nextX = simMarkovMetapop(X = X[i-1], # state
                             c = cc, # colonization rate
                             e = ee, # extirpation rate
                             deltat = time[i]-time[i-1] #delta t
                             )
    X = c(X, nextX)
  }
  aux=data.frame(X = X, time=time, sim=dts)
  data=rbind(data, aux)
}

#adding the non-detected:
ids1 = which(data$X==1)
ids0 = which(data$X==0)

#our favorite beta:
muBeta = rho
nuBeta = 10
alfa = muBeta *nuBeta
beta = (1-muBeta)*nuBeta

# first layer of information degeneration: uncertainty in estimation of true absences
data$X[ids0] = rbeta(n = sum(data$X==0), alfa, beta)

# second layer of information degeneration: flipping of true presences into false absences
aux = rbinom(n = length(ids1), size = 1, prob = rho)

```

```

aux[aux==0] = rbeta(n = sum(aux==0), alfa, beta)

#now flipping our favorite beta:
muBeta = (1-rho)
nuBeta = 10
alfa = muBeta *nuBeta
beta = (1-muBeta)*nuBeta

#finally, converting the datasets:
data$X[ids0] = rbeta(n = length(ids0), alfa, beta)
data$X[ids1] = aux

colnames(data) = c("ppres_mu", "year", "cell")
return(data)
}

```

And the data it produces looks like this (figure 11):

```

rhos = c(0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1)

data=data.frame()
for(i in 1:length(rhos)){
  aux = genDataSetsMetapopRho(ndatasets = 6, c = .1, e = .05, nobs = 15, rho = rhos[i])
  aux$cell=LETTERS[match(aux$cell, 1:6)]
  aux$sim_rho = rhos[i]
  data = rbind(data, aux)
}

ggplot(data, aes(x=year, y=ppres_mu, col=sim_rho))+
  facet_wrap(sim_rho~cell)+
  geom_line()+
  scale_color_gradient(expression(Simulated~rho), low = "plum1", high = "purple4")+
  theme_classic()+
  ylab(expression(psi))+
  theme(legend.position = "bottom")

```

2.3 The information content of a dataset and how it affects the model

Because the metapopulation model we employ has only two states, and because it integrates over uncertain estimates of presence, we should note that some observations have less information than others. For instance, if a given observation $\psi_n = 0.5$, this means that we have no information about the actual state of the cell at t_n . In other words, we have an equal probability of the cell having all the states it can have (i.e., one or zero). Moreover, in the extreme case where the data is a sequence made entirely of repeated $\psi_1 = \psi_n = \psi_N = 0.5$, all the possible transitions (and states) in all possible times are equally likely, and we have no way to extract information to be used for parameter estimation.

Luckily here, this also means that we can directly measure the information content of a given dataset by applying the following function:

$$h(X) = - \sum_{n=1}^N \log_2(1 - |0.5 - \psi_n|)$$

Figure 11: Illustration of 35 different datasets simulated with the same colonization and extirpation rates under imperfect detection ($\psi = 0.5$).

Where $h(X)$, due to the base of the logarithm, is measured in bits (Shannon 1948). The bit is a convenient information unit for our model because it can easily be interpreted: a dataset of arbitrary size and information content $h(X)$ has as much information as a binary dataset (i.e. where $\psi_t \in \{0, 1\}$) of length $h(X)$.

Note that $h(X)$ will always be bounded by the interval $[0, h_N]$, where $h_N = -\log_2(0.5^N)$, and N is the length of the dataset X . In other words, longer sequences have the *potential* to store more information - if they are made of probabilities different from 0.5!

We can implement this function in the following code:

```
h=function(rho){
  aux = -log(1-abs(0.5-rho))
  return(sum(aux))
}
```

```
#testing:
h(rep(0, times=10))
```

```
## [1] 6.931472
```

```
h(rep(1, times=10))
```

```
## [1] 6.931472
```

```
h(rep(0.5, times=10))
```

```
## [1] 0
```

Because longer sequences have an inherently larger capacity to store information when compared to shorter sequences, a straightforward way to compare sequences with different lengths is by measuring their information content relative to their size, where $h_{rel}(X) = \frac{h(X)}{h_N}$, and h_N is the maximum $h(X)$ a certain dataset of length N can have.

2.4 Markov model power analysis

Because multiple factors (dataset length, information content, Markov parameters) can affect our framework's capacity to estimate species values, we conducted power analyses to evaluate the capacity of our likelihood function to estimate simulated parameters under a range of values of colonization rate c , extirpation rate e , length, and information content $h_{rel}(X)$.

Specifically, we simulated the Markov process in our model, where simulated c and e are drawn from a $Unif(0, 1)$, and then estimated parameters using our framework function. To evaluate our power in different scenarios (i.e., where data has different characteristics), we created simulated datasets representative of our data by varying the number of cells used in the estimation (scenarios: 20, 30, 40, 50, 80, 90, 100, 130, 145, 160, 185, and 195 cells), and the number of observations on each cell (scenarios: 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45 observations). Each scenario was evaluated with 1000 simulations, by measuring the R^2 of a no-intercept linear model where the simulated rates are used to predict the estimated rates - thus measuring the amount of variance in the estimates that are aligned with what was simulated.

To evaluate how the amount of information $h(X)$ in a dataset affects our approach's power, we degenerated the information in all scenarios following the probability of sampling ρ and a beta function to generate data analogous to our empirical $\psi_t \in [0, 1]$ but with varying amounts of information. This assumes a specific form

of information degeneration (the one discussed in section 2.2, above) but also allows synthetic analysis of the effect of information content in parameter estimation.

For each simulated presence, we sampled from a *Bernoulli*($p = \rho$) if the presence data should be kept the same (i.e., represent a true presence) or converted to a probability of presence that follows *Beta*($mean = \rho$, "sample size" = 10) (i.e. Supp. Fig. 8). The "sample size" (ν) parameter of this Beta distribution can be interpreted as the effective amount of within-cell patches within the simulated cell, and the smaller its value, the stronger will be the information degeneration due to the fact that fewer patches produce more variable outcomes (which qualitatively follows the predictions made by stochastic metapopulation models as [Alonso & McKane \(2002, Bul. of math. Biol., 64\(5\)\)](#)).

Now, what if the covariance (in Batt et al 2017 case, town temperature) is introducing extra noise in the data? To evaluate this, we need to increase the noise in our simulated data, so we converted all true absences to probabilities of presence that follow a *Beta*($mean = (1 - \rho)$, $sample\ size = 10$). Consequently, the slower the ρ value, the more true, but undetected presences are "flipped" to false absences, and also the less information is left to recover the true sequence of presences and absences, while larger values of ρ approach a dataset to its theoretical maximum amount of information (which is reached when $\rho = 1$). For all scenarios mentioned above, we simulated datasets with ρ equal to 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, and perfect sampling ($\rho = 1$).

In conclusion, the simulations employed here should be seen as a worst-case scenario with respect to variation in the presence estimation, and empirical data, in general, should have less noise if the analyses employed to estimate presence with imperfect detection did capture well the proportion of occupied patches within each cell at a given point in time.

2.5 Power analysis results

As expected, most of the variation in mean h_{rel} among simulations was related to simulated values of ρ (Supplementary Figure 12A, 12B), and h_{rel} in turn impacted our accuracy (i.e., precision and bias). Although there are considerable amounts of noise in estimates ("all" dataset in Supplementary Table 2, supplementary Figure 13A, 13B, Supplementary Figure 14 and 15), if one filters these simulations and only considers datasets where estimated $\tau \in [2^{-7}, 2^4]$ and dataset (i.e. the empirical) $h_{rel} \geq 0.8$, then estimate accuracy increases considerably ("filtered" dataset in Supplementary Table 2, Supp. Fig. 13C, 13D, 16, and 17). Posteriorly, we realised that all species in the empirical dataset that passed in these filters have more than 596 observations, which in practice mean the empirical dataset has more information than some simulations included in the "filtered" simulation set. Thus, we also analysed an additional set of simulations which we labelled "equivalent to empirical".

Scenario-specific scatterplots showing the correlation between simulated and estimated values, as well as the percentage of simulations that lead to estimated values that would be excluded from our empirical filters are shown in Supplementary Figures 14 and 15.

2.6 Power analysis Conclusions

In this section, we describe an important limitation of our approach: the information content of a given dataset, which is indeed the major factor (among those we measured) explaining estimate precision. In particular, we show that only datasets with $h_{rel}(X) \geq 0.8$ provide trustable metapopulation-level estimates because only this level of $h_{rel}(X)$ has enough direct information on extirpation events. This is important to guide sampling efforts in further explorations that follow our approach, as $h_{rel}(X)$ is a property that can be measured and compared among many different datasets.

However, **we advise this may reflect the large size of our empirical dataset**. Indeed, our simulations were based on the properties of our empirical data, and further explorations should be aware that our cutoff of $h_{rel}(X) \geq 0.8$ may not apply in their context. This is especially relevant to studies whose temporal series are shorter than our shortest simulated scenario (i.e. with less than 20 observations in the same time series).

Figure 12: Variation in relative information ($h_{rel}(X)$) in all simulated datasets (panel A), simulated datasets with the same inclusion criteria used in the empirical analysis (panel B), and the empirical dataset (C). Boxplots are grouped by properties of simulated datasets (A & B) and to taxonomic Family (C). This shows that at least in terms of $h_{rel}(X)$ our empirical dataset is likely to behave closely to datasets where $\rho \geq 0.8$, and that $h_{rel}(X)$ seems to not vary according to taxonomic family

Figure 13: Variation in estimate precision using all estimates (panels A and B). Panels C and D show same plots, but subsetting to only consider simulations that match the same criteria we applied to filter the empirical data (“filtered dataset” = estimated $\tau \in [2^{-7}, 2^4]$, and $h_{rel}(X) \geq 0.8$). Sub-panels show simulated ρ . Every point represents a simulated scenario in our power analysis and its sample size varies among panels (=1000 in all points of panels A and B, and is scenario-specific in C and D depending on filtering). The point fill shows the R^2 of a no-intercept linear model where the simulated rates were used to predict the estimated rates. The point frame color shows if scenarios match the smallest number of observations in the empirical dataset (i.e., red has at least 596 observations “equivalent to empirical dataset”, black has fewer). The points represented with a cross instead of a dot are off the color scale in all panels and show scenarios whose $R^2 < 0.001$. As the panels show, by removing clearly “saturated” rates and adopting a minimum h_{rel} , (i.e., by applying the same criteria we did in the empirical estimates), one obtains more accurate estimates (i.e., crosses become circles) - although colonization rate estimates are, in general, more precise.

Figure 14: Scatterplots showing the correlation among simulated (x-axis) and estimated (y-axis, range restricted to simulated values) values of colonization rate. Panel rows show the number of cells simulated and panel columns show classes of hrel. Dashed black lines show 1:1 relationship, and red numbers at each panel show the percentage of simulations outside the limits of the simulated rate values (and so of the plot).

Figure 15: Scatterplots showing the correlation among simulated (x-axis) and estimated (y-axis, range restricted to simulated values) values of extirpation rate. Panel rows show the number of cells simulated and panel columns show classes of hrel. Dashed black lines show 1:1 relationship, and red numbers at each panel show the percentage of simulations outside the limits of the simulated rate values (and so of the plot).

Figure 16: Scatterplots showing the correlation among simulated (x-axis) and estimated (y-axis, range restricted to simulated values) values of colonization rate, with data filtered as the empirical data ($\tau \in [2^{-7}, 2^4]$ and dataset $h_{rel}(X) \geq 0.8$). Panel rows show the number of cells simulated and panel columns show classes of h_{rel} . Dashed black lines show 1:1 relationship, and red numbers at each panel show the percentage of simulations outside the limits of the simulated rate values (and so of the plot).

Figure 17: Scatterplots showing the correlation among simulated (x-axis) and estimated (y-axis, range restricted to simulated values) values of extirpation rate, with data filtered as the empirical data ($\tau \in [2^{-7}, 2^4]$) and dataset $h_{rel}(X) \geq 0.8$. Panel rows show the number of cells simulated and panel columns show classes of h_{rel} . Dashed black lines show 1:1 relationship, and red numbers at each panel show the percentage of simulations outside the limits of the simulated rate values (and so of plot).

In other words, $h(X)$, the absolute amount of information that a dataset has, can be an important factor in other studies and should be investigated in relevant contexts.

Importantly, values of ϵ_{raw} and τ seem to not have a relevant effect on the power of our Markov model, meaning that different regions of the persistence space (See main text) are unbiased with respect to their estimation. However, as it happens with the $h_{rel}(X)$ cutoff, we advise this **lack of estimation bias in the persistence space reflects the decision we made on saturated estimates** (see main text, section “Removal of saturated estimates”). In other words, **the rate in which data is observed delimits the rate of metapopulation change that can be estimated by the model**. This is not particular of our model, but it should be noted regardless.

In summary, although our approach fits many types of data, future investigations that use it should be aware of how factors affecting their particular system and data collection protocols affect what can be estimated. Simulations like those applied in this section can be a good start, but we still have much to learn on what conditions will create the best (and worst) types of datasets to which our approach can be applied.

Importantly, *different models of information degeneration might lead to different results on this particular analysis*, and thus authors interested in applying our framework should feel encouraged to explore different models for information degeneration, and how they influence the threshold of h_{rel} required for accurate parameter estimation.

2.7 Information content in the empirical dataset

Now with all this context added, we can look at the empirical dataset (From Batt et al, 2017) and see (A) how species in the empirical dataset vary in terms of their dataset information content, and, more importantly, if (B) this variation is phylogenetically structured (e.g., if it has phylogenetic signal). To be able to compare species that occur in different numbers of cells (and regions), we would like to measure not only $h(X)$, but also $h_{rel}(X) = h(X)/H_N$. We already briefly explored it in figure 12C, but we will do it more formally below.

For simplicity, we will pick only the species that we actually used in the main text analysis (i.e., the “empirical dataset”, as described in the main text).

We can compare the average $h_{rel}(X)$:

```
dt = read.csv("~/Downloads/pers_spec_rate_Januario_etal/data/final_dataset.csv")

hrelmean = aggregate(dt$hrel, by=list(dt$spp_valid), FUN=mean)

Hrelmean = hrelmean$x
names(Hrelmean) = hrelmean$Group.1

cols = MJtools::makeColorScale2(Hrelmean, hcl.palette = "viridis")
names(cols) = names(Hrelmean)

phy=ape::read.tree("~/Downloads/pers_spec_rate_Januario_etal/data/tree_all_fishes.tre")
phy = ape::keep.tip(phy, names(Hrelmean))

phytools::plotTree.wBars(phy, x = Hrelmean, col=cols, border = NA)

phytools::phylosig(phy, x = Hrelmean, method = "lambda", test = T)

##
## Phylogenetic signal lambda : 0.0776732
```


Figure 18: Phylogenetic distribution of species-averaged $h_{rel}(X)$ (dark colors mean relatively smaller values, and bright colors mean relatively higher values)

```
## logL(lambda) : 302.94
## LR(lambda=0) : 1.25389
## P-value (based on LR test) : 0.262812
```

```
phytools::phylosig(phy, x = Hrelmean, method = "K", test = T)
```

```
##
## Phylogenetic signal K : 0.0476929
## P-value (based on 1000 randomizations) : 0.124
```

And we can compare the variance in $h_{rel}(X)$:

```
hrelvar = aggregate(dt$hrel, by=list(dt$spp_valid), FUN=var)

Hrelvar = hrelvar$x
names(Hrelvar) = hrelvar$Group.1

Hrelvar = Hrelvar[!is.na(Hrelvar)]

cols = MJtools::makeColorScale2(Hrelvar, hcl.palette = "inferno")
names(cols) = names(Hrelvar)

phy=ape::read.tree("~/Downloads/pers_spec_rate_Januario_etal/data/tree_all_fishes.tre")
phy = ape::keep.tip(phy, names(Hrelvar))

phytools::plotTree.wBars(phy, x = Hrelvar, col=cols, border = NA)
```

```
phytools::phylosig(phy, x = Hrelvar, method = "lambda", test = T)
```

```
##
## Phylogenetic signal lambda : 7.50422e-05
## logL(lambda) : 146.119
## LR(lambda=0) : -0.000467108
## P-value (based on LR test) : 1
```

```
phytools::phylosig(phy, x = Hrelvar, method = "K", test = T)
```

```
##
## Phylogenetic signal K : 0.140153
## P-value (based on 1000 randomizations) : 0.692
```

So, here we show species-specific $h_{rel}(X)$ varies, but it **does not** have phylogenetic signal, which allows our straightforward empirical testing done in the main text.

3 Part III: Dealing with biases in the metapopulation model

3.1 Saturating rates

Data generated through Markov processes commonly loses their structure (i.e., *saturate*) when the rate of change is much faster than the timescale in which the system is observed.

Figure 19: Phylogenetic distribution of $h_{rel}(X)$ variance (at species level). Dark colors show relatively smaller values, and bright colors show relatively larger variances. Note here we are including only species that occur in more than one region.

Moreover, the data also have no structure at all if it changes too slowly when compared to the observation timescale. Although this second problem is not related to information saturation *per se*, it will also be addressed in this section.

Because our sampling follows a decadal timescale, we decided that any estimated τ outside the arbitrary bounds of 2^{-7} (= 0.0078 events per year per cell, mean waiting time to next event in a single cell = 128 years), and 2^4 (=16 events per year per cell, mean waiting time to next event in a single cell = 22 days) was likely to represent an unreasonable estimation - plausibly because of saturation in the case of high turnover rates, and because of lack of system change (in terms of cell states) in the case of slow turnover rates. To avoid miscalculating empirical species values, we discarded all species-regions pairs whose τ value (before the linear mixed model (LMM) - see details of this model in the main text) was outside of this same rate range. The rates used to filter out reasonable estimates (mentioned above) are *per capita* rates (i.e., they measure change per year per cell). Thus, when many cells are observed, one can still have enough data to estimate the metapopulation rates in question. We will not simulate how many cells allow the estimation of which parameters because saturation, information content, and dataset size likely interact and a comprehensive exploration of our model is out of the scope of our perspective paper.

Importantly, saturation does not influence our capacity to estimate ϵ . This is because as $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, ϵ becomes the proportion of times a cell will be observed as occupied. This means we do not need to take any additional measures to filter out unreasonable values of ϵ , based on τ estimates. Importantly, we believe τ should be interpreted in the log scale due to the error in the estimate of rates usually being exponential and thus scale-dependent (and we do the same for speciation rate λ).

As we can see in figure 20 (below), few species-region pairs were removed based on these criteria (55 out of 520 - i.e., 10.5%)

3.2 Extreme values of commonness

Some species-region pairs are estimated to have ϵ_{raw} very close to zero or one, but we doubt we have enough numerical precision to estimate such extreme values. This is important because due to the logit-transformation from ϵ_{raw} to ϵ , values of ϵ_{raw} that are very close to zero or one can distort the residuals of our analysis.

These extreme values, in our opinion, appear to reflect properties of the likelihood surface - in particular, they seem characteristic of parameters with a flat or asymptotic likelihood surface in the vicinity of zero. Unfortunately, this property of the likelihood surface also leads to an undesirable numerical phenomenon whereby arbitrary termination of the optimization algorithm at “numerically equivalent” points on the likelihood surface near zero (eg., 0.000001 versus 0.00000000035) can translate into a seemingly large (but spurious) variation on a logit scale.

Thus, we truncated extreme ϵ_{raw} values that are closer to one to $\epsilon_{raw} = 0.9927098$ ($\epsilon = +4.913907$), and we truncated extreme values closer to zero to $\epsilon_{raw} = 0.007290159$ ($\epsilon = -4.913913$). These values were based on the smallest value of ϵ_{raw} estimated that was within the precision of $\frac{1}{N_{patches}}$ for all cells (Pacific sand lance *Ammodytes hexapterus*). This avoided meaningless parameters (ϵ_{raw} smaller than the number of patches), while still allowing meaningful estimates in species that occur in regions with many patches (e.g. the precision that can be obtained in 24 (Southeast US) vs 182 (Newfoundland) patches is not the same). Because ϵ_{raw} and τ are mathematically independent, we did not modified the treatment of τ .

As we can see in figure 21 (below), the consequences of the ϵ_{raw} truncation are almost imperceptible in the “linear” [0, 1] scale, although they are very consequential at the logit-transformed scale:

3.3 Details about the phylo-persistence-space

This space is constructed assuming Brownian motion, estimating node values for each trait independently, and then using Euclidean distances among points as estimates between nodes (Sidlauskas 2008). If persistence

Figure 20: Persistence space for all species-region pairs included in this study, colored by biogeographic region (colors follow main figure 2 and Supplementary Figure 24). The hatched gray area represents the range of values of τ that were included in the empirical analysis shown in the main text. Notice all values of ϵ were maintained by this particular filter (as saturation does not affect ϵ), but as a consequence of the filter based on resilience, we also removed species with extreme values of commonness.

Figure 21: Effect of logit transformations in the persistence space. Points refer to species, and are painted by quadrant in the persistence space following colors used in the main text. Panels show linear (A, C) and logit (B, D) scales. Notice the truncation does not influence much the residuals in the linear scale, but it does so in the logit scale.

syndromes have phylogenetic signal, then clades will cluster in the persistence space. As an additional visualization technique, we projected the estimated values (for nodes and branches) into the persistence space created with just the tips and painted the phylogeny branches following the projected values in Main Figure 3. Under this visualization, phylogenetic signal appeared as closely related branches having similar colors (reflecting their co-occurrence in similar regions of the persistence space - as in main Figure 1C).

4 Part IV: Mixture Markov model

Because the spatial grid within Batt et al (2017) dataset is random with respect to species range or habitat suitability, it is possible that our data samples a spatially heterogeneous mosaic of “sink” and “source” populations, as commonly expected by metapopulation theory (Harrison 1991).

Moreover, even more complex scenarios can be imagined to be important in empirical cases, and thus even the sink-source dichotomy might be overly simplistic to characterize the metapopulation of a species through its range.

Thus, assuming a single demographic process across all cells for a given species risks the extraction of aggregate parameters that average across fundamental differences in metapopulation properties in space, such as those we would expect to observe in source-sink systems. However, cell-specific parametrization would lead to uncertain estimates due to the small amount of observations per cell, as well as potential problems related to overfitting.

We address these complex problems with a simple approach: we consider only two mixtures of metapopulation syndromes, which we label as a and b . The mixture a will describe a proportion $\gamma \in (0, 1)$ of cells, and thus the mixture b will describe the complementary proportion $(1 - \gamma)$ of cells. With this, we relax the assumption of spatially homogeneous colonization-extirpation dynamics within species while maintaining a modest number of parameters per species.

Assuming every individual mixture follows equation (7), the likelihood function of the entire mixture model M_X is:

$$L(\gamma, c_a, e_a, c_b, e_b | M_X) = \gamma \times L(c_a, e_a | X) + (1 - \gamma) \times L(c_b, e_b | X) \quad (9)$$

The model thus integrates over cell class identity without solving it.

In M_X , the modeled metapopulation is fully characterized by 2 combinations of rates (and thus 2 different persistence syndromes), plus a proportion of cells within each mixture. This leads to a total of 5 parameters (i.e., c in sources and sinks, plus e in sources and sinks, plus γ - assuming all sources have the same rates, and all sinks have the same rates). During the optimization of the likelihood of M_X , all 5 parameters are estimated simultaneously.

Alternatively, it is also possible that the species can indeed be characterized by a single persistence syndrome (i.e., only two parameters: c and e for all cells). Indeed the utility of metapopulations as necessary abstractions to understand marine populations has been challenged previously in the literature (Grimm et al, 2003).

We address this as a model selection problem, where the two models competing are the single mixture (eq. 8) and the mixture (eq. 9) models. We optimized the parameters of both models for all species and biogeographic regions and selected the best model by applying $\Delta AICc$.

Thus, if $AICc(M_X) - AICc(no\ mixture) \geq 2.0$, we selected the mixture model and selected the “no mixture” model otherwise.

To characterize the persistence syndrome of a species, we directly picked the estimated rates as species-region pairs when “no mixture” was the best model. However, *if the mixture model was selected*, we pick the rates associated with the mixture with the highest value of $\epsilon_x = c_x / (c_x + e_x)$, to avoid comparing the

“sink” populations of one species to the “source” populations of another. Limitations of this approach are addressed in the discussion section of the main text.

Similarly to saturation (see section 3, above) we will not explore the ability of our mixture modeling framework to correctly infer the simulated amount of mixtures and the rate of every mixture due to the small relevance of the mixture model to our empirical results in the main text. However, one can expect that the amount of metapopulation rate difference, as well as saturation, information content, and dataset size likely interact and a comprehensive exploration of our model is out of the scope of our perspective paper.

As we can see from figure 22, species that were better modeled by the mixture model do not seem to occupy specific quadrants of the persistence space.

Figure 22: Persistence space location of species which were better modeled by a mixture model (blue dots) and that were better modeled by a “no mixture” model (red points)

Finally, it is important to note that within-species variation may also be important when one considers the *meaning* of the measurement of persistence. Incorporating intraspecific variation may be important because knowing that the geographic range of a particular species is mostly made of “sink populations” can be highly informative about the way it persists - even if this is caused by factors that operate at relatively shorter timescales, such as recent fishing, ocean warming, or geologically recent changes in the environment. However, our protocol would discard the cells with low ϵ , which in this context would be representative. This highlights the difficulties of characterizing a species’ complex trait by only a pair of values (or two pairs of values in the case of the mixture model) and the necessity of incorporating spatial breadth and intraspecific variation in future analyses. Incorporating intraspecific variation in persistence is sometimes evoked in the literature as a key frontier of the field (e.g. [Beissinger & Riddell 2021](#)), but measuring this variation will be of little use if we do not develop methods that can base their conclusion on intraspecific variability (among other factors). Those important conceptual problems will remain relevant in future comparative analyses of persistence more broadly, but they are unlikely to change our particular conclusions here due to the small percentage of species best modeled by the mixture model (6.8%, see main text).

5 Part V: Full results on Biogeography-specific persistence patterns

Figures 23 and 24 show complete versions of main figure 2.

Figure 23: Spatial positioning of all cells included in this study, colored by biogeographic region (colors follow main figure 2 and Supplementary Figure 20 and 24).

6 Part VI: Full results on Persistence-speciation patterns

Figure 25 show all combinations of speciation-persistence relationships evaluated in this study.

Figure 24: Biogeographic variation in metapopulation-level persistence. Panels show the region-specific persistence space (i.e., τ and ϵ estimates for each species-region pair, before the LMM), with every point referring to a species-region pair. Black crosses on each panel show 3 standard deviations (and intersection show point estimate) for each random effect in the LMM, and dashed grey lines show, for reference, the median of each persistence axis, considering all species-region pairs. Point colors show biogeographic region (following colors in main figure 2 and Supplementary Figure 22).

Figure 25: Scatterplot showing the relationship between each persistence component (x-axis) and different operationalizations of speciation rate (y-axis). “var. rates” refers to a BAMM model where rates are allowed to vary exponentially through geologic time, while “const. rates” represent time-invariable estimates of speciation rate made with BAMM.